

MULTI-DISCIPLINARY DESIGN OPTIMIZATION OF A HYBRID COMPOSITE FLYWHEEL ROTOR WITH SUPERCONDUCTING MAGNETIC BEARING

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SUMMARY

Multi-disciplinary design optimization is performed to minimize the cost of a composite flywheel satisfying structural safety and dynamic stability. The dynamic stability of a flywheel rotor supported by superconducting magnetic bearings is improved by the implementation of piezoelectric actuator, which optimally changes stiffness and damping coefficient of overall system along with the rotational speed.

Keywords: multi-disciplinary optimization, multi-rim composite flywheel rotor, superconductor magnetic bearing, piezoelectric actuator, rotor dynamic analysis

The multi-disciplinary design optimization (MDO) has been developed to optimize design variables in two disciplines: stress analysis and rotor dynamics of a hybrid multi-rim composite rotor. By optimizing design variables such as inner radius, individual rim thickness, and height, the material cost is minimized. The flowchart shown in Figure 1(a) is the optimization procedure for the rotor which is displayed in Figure 1(b). The six constraints considered are shown in Figure 1(c): the usable energy, capability of the superconducting magnet, the strength ratio of the rotor at zero and maximum rotating speed, as well as the rotor natural frequency. The symbol G stands for a rim of glass/epoxy, C for carbon/epoxy, and G/C for glass/carbon hybrid material. The optimized results are shown in Figure 2.

(a) Flow chart of the multi-disciplinary optimization

(b) Schematic diagram of hybrid multi-rim rotor

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{Find } r_i, \omega, t_h, t_i \quad (i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 6) \\
 & \text{Minimize Cost} \\
 & \text{Subject to Usable energy} > 100 \text{ kWh} \\
 & \quad \text{mass} < 2000 \text{ kg} \\
 & \quad R^{(i)} < 0.6 \text{ at } \omega = \omega_{\max} \\
 & \quad R^{(i)} < 0.6 \text{ at } \omega = 0 \\
 & \quad R^{(i)} = \max(R_y^{(i)}, R_g^{(i)}, R_{\sigma=30}^{(i)}) \\
 & \quad \text{First bending frequency} > 30,000 \text{ rpm}
 \end{aligned}$$

(c) Optimization formula

Figure 1. Multi-disciplinary design optimization of a flywheel rotor.

Figure 2. Optimized results.

Since the superconducting magnetic bearing-flywheel energy storage system (SMB-FESS) has lower stiffness and smaller damping coefficient than other contactless bearings like active magnetic bearing (AMB), it has lower whirl natural frequencies. The first backward whirling mode has much smaller excitation force than the second forward whirling mode, which is shown in Figure 3(a). To prevent the resonance caused by the second forward whirling mode of the SMB-FESS, stiffness and damping coefficient are changed using piezoelectric actuator. The green and blue curves in Figure 3(b) show the original and changed vibration characteristics of SMB-FESS, respectively. When the rotating speed is less than approximately 135 rpm or greater than approximately 200 rpm, the SMB-FESS remains untouched; if the rotating speed is between those two values mentioned above, the piezoelectric actuator is activated, so that the great resonance of the original system, which is shown as the green peak, is avoided. The red curve in Figure 3(b) clearly shows the enhancement of the dynamic stability of the SMB-FESS through the utilization of piezoelectric actuator.

Figure 3. Enhancement of dynamic stability of FESS using piezoelectric actuator for adjusting stiffness and damping coefficients.